

FACTORS INFLUENCING GROUP WORK OF STUDENTS' ACADEMIC SUCCESS IN QUALITATIVE APPROACH

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Annotation: The aim of this study is to explore the high achieving students' perceptions of factors contributing the academic achievement. To accomplish this purpose, the study utilizes qualitative narrative approaches, documenting the experiences of high school students through focus group discussions, responses to open-ended questionnaires and drawing of students past and current experiences.

Keywords: Academic performance, success factors, failure factors, students' perspective, teachers' perspective, relationship, implications.

Education is an important part of human life as well as human resource development. The dictionary meaning of the word "Education" is 'the process of facilitating learning and acquiring knowledge, skills, development, morals, and beliefs'.

It is an all-encompassing term that includes the development of various kinds of skill-set, be it academic, professional, physical, or creative.

Although "being educated" carries the deep meaning of acquiring these skill sets, according to individual will and talent, it is often mistaken to be purely Academic.

Academic education also helps children develop deeper interests in various subjects that play a part in deciding the professional trajectory of an individual. Every student is taught the significance of a good academic record, to become a stable, successful individual and to help pick out a fruitful career. It is important for a student to perform well in academics, especially during higher secondary school, to secure university scholarships, have a choice of subjects to study in college, and to ensure the stability of career and enjoy economic freedom during adulthood.

However, every student faces a phase in their student lives, when their academic performance is deeply affected due to outside factors that may be disturbing for them.

Group work has been used in classrooms in various ways and for various reasons. Literature I have read and experiences I have gained in university classrooms have helped me to form several working hypotheses for the research project, which had the following research question: What enhances and impedes group work as a learning situation, seen from the students' perspective?

First of all I expected that the students would learn a great deal in their work groups. The theories I have read and the experiences I have gained for the most part positively coloured my researcheye. All the same, I expected to find some 'free riders' in the groups, and I anticipated that the students had various expectations or ambitions for their work. I have also experienced that different writing styles can create problems in groups. If the students have different living conditions, this could become a problem, and different education, life-experience and work-experience backgrounds could also complicate the group work (Postholm, 2004). Moreover, disagreement on the content in the collaboration process and role problems can also impede the group processes (Johnson & Johnson, 2006; McMaster & Fuchs, 2002; Slavin, 1996). I have previously experienced that various ambitions can create problems in groups (Postholm, 2004).

As we have seen, the students in this course also started with different ambitions, but that the ambition level rose during the work process. Their continuous work on the writing tasks and the continuous feedback they received from the teacher throughout the process motivated them for the work and to expect a good result. Many deadlines or pauses, including breaks to give feedback as support and help to move on, really seems to motivate the students. This shows that student efforts and continuous follow-up by teachers can encourage the students to work more and thus increase their learning. The students think that the studies and their structure compel them to work hard but that this setting or situation also encourages them to work together when they become frustrated. My anticipation about various ambitions was first confirmed, but during the process it was disproved.

References:

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